

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Procedures of irregularisation in Greece: spatial, carceral and temporal aspects

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Table of Contents

Abstract	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Methodology	6
3. Conceptualising irregularisation	7
4. The immigration policy framework in Greece: a regime of irregularisation .	11
5. The Greek asylum system: an emerging labyrinth of irregularisation	14
5.1 Who deserves protection? Registration, complex asylum procedures and profiling.....	15
5.2 Criminalising asylum seekers' practices by depriving them from reception provisions	17
5.3 Safe third country inadmissibility & suspension of readmissions to Turkey.....	18
5.4 Irregularisation during processes of notification of decision and appeals	21
5.5 An ambiguous return framework of coercion that reinforces irregularisation.....	22
5.6 Irregularisation as process: The stories data (don't) tell	24
6. Intersecting Layers of Irregularisation	28
6.1 Temporal.....	28
6.2 Spatial.....	31
6.3 Carceral	34
7. Concluding remarks	38
References	40

List of abbreviations

ADET	Uniform-Format Residence Permit
AMKA	National Insurance Number
AVRR	Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration
CCAC	Closed Controlled Access Centres
CJEU	Court of Justice of the European Union
CPT	European Committee for the Prevention of Torture and Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
ECtHR	European Court of Human Rights
EIL	Enforcement of immigration legislation
EU	European Union
GAS	Greek Asylum Service
GCR	Greek Council for Refugees
IO	International Organisation
IOM	International Organization for Migration
JMD	Joint Ministerial Decision
MMA	Ministry of Migration and Asylum
MS	Member State
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PAAYPE	Temporary Insurance and Health Care Number
PRDC	Pre-Removal Detention Center
RIC	Reception and Identification Center
RMI	Return Migration Infrastructure
SOP	Standard Operating Procedures
TCN	Third-country national

Abstract

This working paper explores how the irregularisation of migration is produced and reproduced through the workings of the legal and institutional framework of migration and asylum in the case of Greece. Irregularity is not considered here only as a legal status (or the absence of it), but as the outcome of policies, institutional arrangements, and the formal and informal practices of various actors within the wider political and socio-economic context. We thus discuss irregularisation as a process rather than a state of things, one in which many (also ‘regular’) people may be involved, in sequences of (ir)regular statuses. Irregularisation entails a sum of diverse informal or ‘irregular’ or ‘illegal’ practices that also people with ‘regular’ statuses develop in order to navigate in the otherwise hostile migration and asylum regime.

The paper examines in short how irregularisation has emerged through the immigration system over the last three decades including the complicated pathways to regularisation procedures, and the police practices. It then focuses on the labyrinth of irregularisation that has been reproduced through the newly established asylum system after 2015-16, in all the stages of an asylum application: the initial registration of the asylum claim; the asylum procedure and the multiple categories of deservingness/undeservingness it creates; the so called inadmissible claims related to the safe third country rule and the recent suspension of readmissions to Turkey; the irregularisation and criminalisation of asylum seekers’ practices by reducing or withdrawing reception provisions; the appeal procedure; and the return policy framework characterised by coercion reinforcing irregularisation, even in cases of self-proclaimed ‘voluntary’ returns.

The paper also analyses the spatial and temporal dimensions of the process of irregularisation, starting from even before border-crossing and extending during the diverse routes along which legislation and institutional practices create borders and categorise people. Moreover, the crucial role that is reserved for migrants’ deprivation of liberty (even for those applying –or having already applied– for asylum) calls for a separate examination of the carceral dimension that affects dramatically migrants’ pathways in space and time in the contemporary migration regimes.

The spatial and temporal boundaries among the figures of the (il)legal, the (ir)regular, the registered, the detained, the returnee, the deportee, and the asylum-seeker are blurred, as are the experiences and the statuses of those emplaced in these spaces and temporalities. Overall, as the paper argues, irregularisation is both produced by laws and their implementation but is also productive in itself in spatial, temporal and carceral terms. As some recent developments in the EU system of migration governance show, Greece can be considered as a showcase and a field of experimentation for irregularisation in Europe.

Keywords:

Process of irregularisation, migration and asylum policies, asylum procedures, space-time, detention, Greece

1. Introduction¹

The aim of the Working Paper is to explore and critically analyse the notion of irregularisation, and particularly to examine how it emerges through legislation and institutional procedures in the case of Greece. Its objective is twofold. First, to discuss irregularisation not in terms of the status of irregularity, but as a dynamic and evolving process in which many (also ‘regular’) people may be entangled. The process of irregularisation consists of sequences of regular and irregular statuses, but also of informal, or ‘irregular’, or, ‘illicit’, or ‘illegal’ practices that also people with ‘regular’ status may develop in their efforts to navigate the complex and restrictive legal frameworks of asylum and immigration. Second, the paper aims to unpack and explore the different dimensions in which irregularisation as a process unfolds, namely the procedural, the spatial, the temporal, and the carceral. We seek to explore how irregularisation is (re)produced at the intersections of these overlapping layers.

More precisely, our research questions are the following:

- i. What are the institutional procedures that irregularise individuals and groups? What is the place of these procedures in the legal framework on migration and asylum and in its implementation in practice?
- ii. What is the temporality of irregularisation? How does it change in the long run of changing migration and asylum policies? What are the tempos, the paces and the duration of irregularisation procedures in the sort run of individual trajectories?
- iii. What is the spatiality of irregularisation? Which are the geographical routes that are affected and the places where it occurs?
- iv. How is irregularisation entangled with the detention of migrants and asylum seekers?

2. Methodology

Methodologically, the Working Paper is based on both desk and primary research conducted as part of the GAPs ‘De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond’ project. Desk research, included the study of the institutional framework, national laws and legal provisions, policy documents, official reports, statistical data, EU-related documents, as well as reports from a number of actors involved in the field of migration and asylum such as International Organisations (IOs) and Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs). Primary research included mainly qualitative methods exploring the concept of ‘Return Migration Infrastructures’ (RMIs). Research on RMIs aims to bring to the fore how return migration governance is put into practice, by focusing on: the actors involved in the operation of returns, their relationships and networks, their everyday practices, the different steps of the return process, and the materials and technologies that shape the ways in which returns take place on the ground. In Greece, research on RMIs involved sixteen (16) semi-structured interviews with stakeholders and actors engaged in the implementation of returns, a focus on the Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) program, run by the

¹ The authors would like to thank the GAPs coordinators Zeynep Şahin Mencütek (Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies) and Soner Barthoma (Uppsala University), as well as Anna Triandafyllidou (Canada Excellence Research Chair in Migration and Integration, Toronto Metropolitan University) for their constructive comments and suggestions that improved the paper. The authors are also grateful to the members of the Stakeholder Experts Panel formed in Greece and their invaluable insights provided during the first SEP & EKKE team meeting that was held on the 4th of October 2023, as well as to actors’ representatives that accepted to be interviewed for the needs of the GAPs project.

International Organization for Migration (IOM), as an ‘entry point’ for the research, as well as ethnographic methods in constituting parts of the particular RMI.

More particularly, interviews were conducted with representatives of national authorities, IOs, and NGOs, as well as of migrant and refugee communities and organisations. The selection of stakeholders started by focusing on the actors implementing the AVRR program, particularly IOM and its different teams/departments responsible for the implementation of the different parts of the return procedure. Gradually, a number of other actors were approached related to the management and planning of AVRR in other scales, including state authorities, such as the Ministry of Migration and Asylum (MMA). Participants also included actors engaged with other types of RMIs in Greece, notably forced returns and pushbacks: NGOs, institutional bodies, and commissions related to the monitoring of returns, human rights and legal advocacy. In an infrastructural perspective, these interviews constituted a tool to explore the relations and interactions between actors, materials, and technologies that together mediate the ways in which returns take place. The majority of interviews were conducted in the actors’ premises, while few were conducted online or at National Centre for Social Research’s (EKKE’s) offices. Most lasted about one hour, while some lasted much more, approaching the two hours. In all cases, participants offered their informed written consent.

Field research also included ethnographic visits and observations in different localities, places, premises, and offices, all being constituent parts of the RMIs in Greece. These included the IOM headquarters where a number of services are provided and where most procedures take place, the Athens airport as part of the material dimensions of the AVRR infrastructure, and the Open Centre for migrants registered for AVRR (OCAVRR), where beneficiaries are provided temporary accommodation in Athens. The research team conducted ethnographic research through field visits and guided tours by IOM representatives in these three places, strictly adhering to the ‘do no harm’ principle towards research participants and other people present in these places at the time of the visits.

3. Conceptualising irregularisation

In this Working Paper **irregularity is understood as a process rather than a fixed condition, a state of things, a characteristic or ‘quality’ that certain people possess** (also in Näre et al., 2024); a process which is ‘above all a product of the law’ (Jacobsen & Karlsen, 2020: 10) deriving from the ever restrictive and highly complex migration and asylum policies (Näre et al., 2024; Triantafyllidou & Spencer 2020; Ambrosini, 2016; De Genova, 2002). Irregularity entails a number of informal, or ‘irregular’, or ‘illegal’ practices that both ‘irregular’ and ‘regular’ people develop in order to navigate within the otherwise hostile migration and asylum system along their shifting migratory projects and trajectories.

Irregularity has increasingly been a major reference point in dominant public discourses concerning migration. Irregularity becomes defined through normative antithesis: regularity or actually legality. Thus irregularity is interpreted through a simplified lens of a binary good (legal, regular) and problematic (irregular which gets equated with illegal) that may easily be employed in scapegoating ‘irregulars’ as threats to the social and political (national and EU) body.

The ‘illegal’ migrant together with the ‘bogus’ asylum seeker have been pivotal figures around whom political discourses on migration (control) and migration and asylum policies have been shaped and reshaped over the past decades (see also Balibar, 2010; Mezzadra, 2015). Yet the ‘shades’ of il/legality, ir/regularity and un/deservingness are never so clear-cut as they

are often presented to be. Rather they entail multi-faceted and complex categorisations that reflect the changing political conjunctures and employment/labour needs in a particular context that deem a migrant as deserving.

Irregularity involves multiple categories, conditions and experiences, ‘including those who remain on state territory after having overstayed their visa, having had their residency revoked or asylum application rejected or never having applied for residency or asylum’ (Jacobsen & Karlsen, 2020: 1; similarly in Triandafyllidou & Spencer, 2020: 2). Notions of ‘semi-legality’ or ‘befallen irregularity’ (see Triandafyllidou & Bartolini, 2020; Triandafyllidou, 2023) have been coined to describe not only the multiple categorisations but also the transience of ir/regularity. In order to represent the diverse ways that people might end up in irregular statuses, Näre et al (2024: 10) in their comparative report for I-CLAIM project, identify three main routes into administrative irregularity and precarity in the six I-CLAIM countries: the administrative, the demographic and the geographic one. As Savatic et al. (2024: 3) argue, ‘the distribution across categories depends upon visa and asylum policies’ and ‘states are trapped in a circular logic: migration and asylum policies determine how many border-crossers are counted and whether they are labelled as “refugees” or “(ir)regular migrants” making states the origin of the distinction that then subsequently requires distinct policies’.

This complex categorisation and hierarchical positioning of migrants along the spectrum of ir/regularity is, according to De Genova (2015: 3-4), ‘the work of immigration regimes and citizenship law’ as well as product of ‘the bordered definition of state territoriality that constitutes particular forms and expressions of human mobility as ‘migration’ and classifies specific kinds of people who move as “migrants”’. Criminalisation along with illegalisation frame the ways irregularity and irregularisation is understood in many EU policies (Näre et al., 2024: 9), while its conceptualisation is territorially bounded to the irregular crossing of the external Schengen borders (ibid) and on irregularly staying in an EU country.

Since states often consider deportations difficult to conduct, apprehending mobility is prompted by an array of measures for securitising and militarising the multiple borders, by criminalising border-crossings (Macias-Rojas, 2021) as well as by de-territorialising asylum claims (as for example in the case of ‘the fiction of non-entry’ in the New Pact). Moreover, as Klaus and Szulecka (2023) discuss ‘another technique often used is the creation of a hostile environment on legal, practical, economical or discursive levels to try to encourage people to depart, to leave the country “voluntarily”’.

Deportability, bearing the ‘ability’ to be deported at any time, relies exactly on demarcations of (migrant but not only) illegality and their border practices. Despite claims for being ineffective, deportation regimes and deportability per se, impact on the exploitation, the vulnerability but also on the broader economies of migration and security regimes (see also Karadag & Sert, 2023). Hence, De Genova (2010) contends that deportability of migrants has ‘to be seen in a continuum with “detainability”’ as well as with other modalities of ‘captivity and confinement’.

Actually, and increasingly, someone can be labelled as ‘illegal’ even before any legal decisions or irrespective of them (as has been the case in 2020 with the tensions in Evros at the Greek-Turkish borders and elsewhere). Thus illegality becomes a de facto attribute inscribed into the bodies and identities of migrants crossing borders (albeit not to all migrants’ groups since it tends to be nationality driven). As Jansen writes, ‘and today, while Frontex is operating on the European borders—which have been extended far beyond the EU—and people regularly drown, suffocate or suffer and die by other means, it is their “illegal” movement which still tends to be perceived first and colours perception of their death, detention or deportation’ (Jansen, 2015: 16).

As (illegalised) migrants continue to incarnate a major ‘threat’ in European discourses, migration is increasingly perceived as something ‘irregular’ and thus managing this irregularity and securitising the core body of the EU becomes a key priority, resulting in the proliferation of border practices and bio- and necro-political governance of migrants (see De Genova, 2015). As Jansen et al argue (2019: ix), ‘the irregularisation of migration and the increase of border policing are processes standing in close connection to the free flow of labour, commodities and money in a globalised economy. The smoothing of mercantile space goes hand in hand with –and indeed seems to facilitate– an ever more complex stratification of geographical space and a dismantling of rights and political agency. In that context, borders could be said to differentiate among populations –to create different spaces for different populations even– and increasingly so, down to the level of the individual’. Similarly, Mezzadra and Neilson (2013: 7) observed that border practices instigate a form of ‘differential inclusion’ that ‘select and filter people and different forms of circulation in ways no less violent than those deployed in exclusionary measures’. Yet this practice of differentiation, also results in differentiated rights for different categories of people depending on the place and time of border practices and on people’s nationality. It may also result in differentiated ‘deportability’ and ‘inhabitation’ of the grey spaces of irregularisation that we will see further on.

Finally, illegality is not only produced but is productive in itself. As several scholars have discussed (De Genova, 2002; Triantafyllidou & Spencer, 2020; Ambrosini, 2016) irregularisation produces an exploitable and vulnerable workforce living under constant threat. Ruben Anderson (2014: 7, 15) studied the ‘illegality industry’ flourishing in European borderlands, to highlight ‘not the repressive but the productive nature’ of migration and border controls, in particular ‘how the “management” of irregular migration is a particularly expensive -and lucrative- field’. The concept, he argued, ‘allows for the consideration of a dispersed “value chain”, or the distinct domains in which migrant illegality is processed, “packaged”, presented, and ultimately rendered profitable’ for a wide and diverse array of actors including rentier states and employers, smuggling networks and security companies, border guards and aid workers, the media and academia (Anderson, 2014) This industry, ‘feeding on the illegality it is meant to control, only produces more and increasingly distressing forms of it’ (Anderson, 2014: 24).

There are several insights from the literature on the so-called migration industries (e.g. Gammeltoft-Hansen & Sorensen, 2013) and political economic critiques to migration controls which are relevant here. From lobbying strategies of private contractors managing detention facilities who push for expanding detention (Conlon & Hiemstra, 2014), to Frontex’s incentives to count more irregular/illegal border crossings in order to depict unauthorised migration as a problem ‘which requires a securitised response - a response that it can provide if given more resources’ (Savatic et al., 2024: 25). In the carceral landscape of the wider borderlands, according to Achtnich (2022: 112, 98-9), ‘the precarious migrant body becomes part of a transnational system of economic production..., subjected to multiple rounds of value extraction’. Along similar lines of thought, Martin (2021: 747) argued that ‘legal categorisation is foundational’ in producing what she calls ‘carceral economies of migration control’, analysing, among others, how ‘status value’ is created by the ‘illegalisation of mobile people’ allowing for the commodification of migrant life not ‘as property but as assemblages of services, bed space, data and mobility’.

Although a great part of this discussion oscillates between legalities and illegalities, analysing the complexities of the multiplicities of laws (akin to the multiplication of borders) and taking into consideration the ad-hoc legal suspension (Sundberg, 2015: 210; also Agamben, 2006) that is increasingly ‘normalised’ (as for example the recent and now

institutionalised border closures depriving asylum seekers from their rights) can provide an additional vantage point for analysing irregularisation. Hence, in this multitude of laws and regulations, one could argue that irregularisation, besides being a product of political will and interests, is also engendered by an over-regulation and an obscured/invisibilised implementation (that exploits the legal ‘gaps’ and ‘invisibilised’ practices such as pushbacks etc.).

Considering the spectrum that constitutes irregularisation and the fact that irregularisation unfolds in multiple spatialities, temporalities and legalities, the socio-spatial notions of informality and of ‘grey spaces (Yiftachel, 2009a; 2009b) might further enrich its theorisation. Sahin-Mencutek and Triandafyllidou (forthcoming) contend that although informality has been explored as a way ‘in which migrants navigate mobility or immobility’, its role ‘in migration governance has not been sufficiently theorized’. Therefore, they suggest that ‘formality and informality intersect in governing returns leading to a sort of “messy governance” which is intentional.

The intentional aspect of informality has been extensively discussed in the respective scholarship. By bringing in dialogue research on migrant illegalisation and critical poverty scholarship, De Genova and Roy (2020) argue that ‘the study of practices of illegalisation allows critical poverty scholarship to better discern how sociopolitical categories and classifications that are central to wider processes of marginalisation and domination may arise or be reinforced as effects of the state’s legal productions of illegality’. Correspondingly, seeing migrant irregularisation through the lens of informalisation supports our understanding of informality as a process that takes place both at the edges of the legal and illegal and at the whole spectrum in-between, ‘in the shadows of formal and informal’ and handled ‘by employing a range of delegitimising and criminalising discourses, regulations and violence’ (Yiftachel, 2009b: 243).

Writing on informality and on the ‘coming apartheid’ in Israel, Yiftachel (2009a; 2009b), with a more spatial outlook, describes grey space as referring to ‘developments, enclaves, populations and transactions positioned between the “lightness” of legality/approval/safety and the “darkness” of eviction/destruction/death. Grey spaces are neither integrated nor eliminated, forming pseudo-permanent margins of today’s urban regions, which exist partially outside the gaze of state authorities and city plans’. Discussing about practices of illegalisation of migrant and non-migrant populations, De Genova and Roy (2020) refer to cut-off dates (for legalisation or amnesties) as a powerful spatio-temporal technology, reinscribing legality and illegality and renewing relationships of political loyalty and dependency. Scholarship on urban informality has paid close attention to cut-off dates as a way of understanding the ‘temporal rhythms’ of statecraft, especially in relation to those ‘who live on the margins of the state’ (De Genova and Roy, 2020: 7). Temporariness, and specifically permanent temporariness is also a key feature of grey spaces (Yiftachel, 2009a; 2009b) but also of irregularisation whereby immobilisation, lack of foreseeable future, ‘temporary accommodation’ or ‘temporary protection visas’ complement the aforementioned ‘temporal rhythms’ of the state.

Wanting to underline the deeply racialised and exclusive /expelling aspects of deportability, Kalir (2019) employs the notion of ‘departheid’. ‘Departheids formal goal to maintain a national territory vacated of illegalised migrants is to be achieved by the deployment of legal, psychological, and physical violence at three key sites: first, at the point of entry, states fortify and protect borders to pre-emptively deny entrance to those who, it is suspected, will become illegalised migrants; second, inside their sovereign territory, states segregate and confine illegalised migrants to specially designated waiting zones’—neighborhoods, camps, hotspots, prisons, and detention facilities—from where surveillance and controlled removals can be

more easily managed; third, at the point of exit, states oblige illegalised migrants to “voluntarily leave” or be forcefully deported’ (Kalir 2019: 20).

Triantafyllidou and Bartolini (2020: 13) suggest conceptualising irregular migration ‘as a continuum of different statuses between regularity and irregularity’. In this sense, we can conceptualise irregularisation (the process of becoming irregular) as a process navigating multiple grey spaces, temporalities and legalities that produce transient and transitional irregularities.

4. The immigration policy framework in Greece: a regime of irregularisation

The notion of ‘multifaceted labyrinth’, through which Tsitselikis (2019) characterised the complex asylum system established in Greece after 2015, is probably appropriate to describe the entire immigration regime as it has been established since the 1990s. It is when Greece is known to have transformed from a country of emigration to a destination and transit country due to the increase of immigrant arrivals mainly from Balkan and Eastern European countries, predominantly from Albania.

Back then, the state’s unpreparedness and the lack of a coherent immigration policy were marked in practice by a contradictory combination. Migrant irregularity was, on the one hand, criminalised through excessive policing (Kourtovic, 2001), involving border patrols, internal controls and mass deportations (Baldwin-Edwards & Fakiolas, 1998; Maroukis, 2008). On the other, it was tolerated for serving a quasi-laissez-faire approach feeding the labour market with needed cheap and flexible work (Lazaridis & Poyago-Theotoki, 1999; Hatziprokopiou 2006). Early institutional arrangements have contributed to the creation of an ethnic hierarchy as migrants considered as of Greek origin were the only ones to receive some kind of integration assistance (Triandafyllidou & Veikou 2002; Kandylis 2006). The majority encountered strict requirements for legal residence and complicated and discouraging regularisation procedures that forced them into a perpetual state of limbo between legality and illegality (Triandafyllidou & Veikou 2002; Marvakis 2004; Kandylis 2006; Hatziprokopiou 2006).

Since the late 1990s, successive Greek governments focused on regulating the stay and work of people already living in the country. In light of the forthcoming 2004 Olympic Games, and in parallel with the deepening xenophobic and racist perceptions towards migrants (Ventoura, 2004), large-scale regularisation processes took place in order to ensure the worker status of previous undocumented migrants (Lazaridis & Poyago-Theotoky, 1999). Cheap and precarious migrant labour, especially in construction, agriculture and domestic services, contributed to the high rates of economic growth of that period. Despite seemingly decreasing, deportations of irregular migrants never ceased to take place, with a number of them constituting land pushbacks.

The post-2008 debt crisis significantly impacted the sociopolitical circumstances, as well as experiences of irregularisation. Situations of ‘befallen irregularity’ (Triandafyllidou, 2023) with the sharp rise in unemployment affecting disproportionately migrants, as the longstanding requirement of submitting proof of formal employment in order to renew a stay permit led

many settled immigrants back to irregularity (Pratsinakis et al., 2017)². Deepening inequalities affecting the migrant population have been very much due to ‘periodic transitions from legal to illegal residence status and long-lasting periods in an ambiguous legal status’ which ‘remained the norm for many of the established immigrants and most newcomers’ (Kandylis & Maloutas, 2017: 136). Worsening life conditions were exploited to augment xenophobia, racist discourses, and discrimination against migrants. Meanwhile, naturalisation, the sole route to full participation rights, has been notably difficult to access for the majority (Mavromatis, 2018; Gogonas & Tramountanis, 2023).

The early 2010s were characterised by a dominant discourse insisting on the ‘war against illegal migration’ (Papatzani & Petracoou, 2022). Specific policies were implemented in this regard, with a shift of emphasis to sealing the border. The Law 3907/2011 was adopted to transpose the Directive 2008/115/EC on common standards and procedures for returning illegally staying TCNs. Securitisation of borders was enhanced, especially through the adoption of the ‘Integrated Border Management Program for Combating Illegal Immigration’ in 2011, whose main targets were ‘the protection of both the EU and national borders’, and the ‘reduction of the illegal migration’ (Ministry of Citizen Protection, 2011). This program included -among others- the construction of the Evros fence in the southeast borders of Greece, described as a ‘technical barrier’ that will combat ‘illegal’ migration (Ministry of Citizen Protection, 2011). Despite its cost in a period of economic crisis, ‘national-level discourse by political actors reveals that the construction of the fence was linked to the wider EU-level migration and border control practices, as well as to the national-level perception of migration as a security issue’ (Grigoriadis & Dilek, 2019: 171). At the same time, a system of pre-removal detention centres was established with a Ministerial Decision in 2015, regulating already existing detention facilities.

Even though border controls had been tightening, applying for asylum (even if one is aware of the limited possibilities for a positive decision and that the application could involve detention in case of arrest), had been a main pathway to some kind of regularity. Asylum, after all, has long been a main ‘corridor’ for many migrants entering Greece in search of safety and/or better life prospects in the country or some other EU member state, even well before 2015 (Papatzani et al., 2022a). In the absence of legal routes and in the context of limited opportunities for regularisation, a significant number of undocumented migrants were granted residence permit for humanitarian reasons (‘Humanitarian status’). The Humanitarian Status was granted to undocumented migrants based on the Law 4251/ 2014 (art.19A, par.1) and Law 4375/2016 (art. 22) mainly until 2015 as a first instance decision. Until 2020 it was granted at second instance and referred to a significant number of positive decisions. Recently, these provisions were abolished by the Law 4825/2021 (art.72).

During the last few years, two legal arrangements were adopted that promoted migrants regularisation. The first is the Memorandum of Understanding ‘for immigration and mobility’ signed by Greece and Bangladesh ratified by Law 4959/2022. The Memorandum sets out the conditions of entry and temporary residence of Bangladeshi nationals who have been staying in Greece before 9 February 2022 for the purpose of temporary employment. The permit is valid for 5 years, the permit holders are required to return to Bangladesh for at least 3 months per year, and once the permit expires, they have no right to renew or apply for another residence permit and are required to leave the country. This legislation put about 11,000 irregular workers, mainly in the agricultural economy, in the process of regularisation, aiming

² Additional legislation came to address what has been, e.g. by reducing the number of social insurance stamps required as proof of legal employment, by speeding up procedures for permit renewals, or by opening up access to longer duration of residence permits (Triandafyllidou, 2014).

to end the phenomena of exploitation revealed by the landmark judgment of the ECtHR 'Chowdhury and others VS Greece' (2017), the well-known case of Manolada (Kerasiotis, 2024). The same year Greece and Egypt signed an Agreement ratified by Law 5009/2023 for the employment of seasonal workers in the agricultural sector. The second legal arrangement is the Law 5078/2023 (art. 193) granting a new type of residence permit for work, acting as a broad regularisation for undocumented migrants. The main characteristics of this three-year permit, among others, include the requirement of three years of previous residence in the country and a certificate from the employer that the person is going to work for him/her; and the possibility of subsequent renewal to any other type of residence permit.

Pragmatic labour market considerations seem to be at the heart of these recent legal initiatives, following about a decade of policies aimed primarily at regulating asylum and building a reception system at the expense of established migrants and their offspring (Christopoulos, 2020). Our interviews revealed, on the one hand, that a number of asylum seekers whose applications have been rejected, especially from nationalities with 'low recognition rates' (e.g. Pakistan), apply for residence permit, giving an – at least temporal until the decision on their application – end to their irregular status that followed the asylum decision on their cases. On the other, it has been argued that the initial attempts to implement the aforementioned measures have been problematic, as immigration services across the country interpret the law in different ways. A striking example is the requirement for undocumented migrants to present a rent contract in their name when applying, despite the Immigration Code clearly stating that contracts cannot be issued to TCNs without legal documents (Kerasiotis, 2024). Additionally, various issues arise concerning the proof of uninterrupted three-year residence in the country. Decentralised administrations often reject documents of certain date despite the not restrictive mention in the law's circular, and despite the fact that it is widely known that undocumented individuals often lack any form of documentation. These examples of administrative abuse put a significant portion of the population at risk and the regularisation will likely benefit far fewer people than anticipated (Kerasiotis, 2024).

Irregularisation does not derive solely by regulations on paper, but also from institutional practices that have been implemented throughout the years. As already mentioned, the large-scale deportations of irregular Albanian migrants- widely known as 'sweep operations' - were performed by the police on the streets, as a means to combat irregular migration enjoying wide coverage in the national media, yet on the fringes of official legal rules (Baldwin-Edwards & Fakiolas, 1998; Maroukis, 2008). Such police practices were enhanced within the context of the economic crisis, when xenophobia and racism re-increased substantially (Baldwin-Edwards, 2014). During the early 2010s, as part of the aforementioned 'Integrated Border Management Program for Combating Illegal Immigration' the 'Xenios Zeus' police 'sweep' operation was launched in urban centers since 2012. The operation - ironically called Xenios Zeus akin to the ancient God of hospitality - had the explicit purpose of combating 'illegal migration and criminality' (Xenakis & Cheliotis, 2013). It has been implemented through patrols and raids targeting immigrants on the streets, followed by massive arrests aiming at identifying and subsequently deporting irregular migrants. What this campaign brought about was not so much an increase of deportation, but a significant increase of the number of people imprisoned in harsh conditions in pre-removal detention centres around Greece, even for periods longer than two years (HRW, 2012; 2013). The daily interactions between the police authorities and migrants marked by regularly reported incidents of violation of rights and abuse and associated with massive detention (Pavlou, 2009; Karamanidou, 2016), while controls and search of documented migrants on the streets put also them in situations of

uncertainty in everyday life (Papatzani, 2021) blurring the boundaries between regularity and irregularity.

Overall, we could argue that the legal, policy, and institutional framework of immigration has diachronically reproduced a regime of irregularisation, since the transformation of Greece into a destination country in the 1990s. Both the regulations on paper, including their transformations over the years, and the institutional practices implemented by different actors, especially on the part of the police authorities, have determined the protracted nature of irregularity as a condition and the different sequences of regular and irregular statuses that define immigrants' irregularisation as a process. The above have also determined migrants' experiences, which have mostly been characterised by legal limbo and a series of restrictions, followed by periods when residence permits offered more opportunities to improve living conditions, before being restricted again, e.g. after the expiry of the permits, due to their short-term nature.

5. The Greek asylum system: an emerging labyrinth of irregularisation

Prior to 2011, the asylum system in Greece suffered from chronic structural deficiencies. It was characterised by extremely low recognition rates of only few asylum applications with the majority rejected at the first instance. Indicatively, from 2009 to 2013, there were approximately 10,000 to 15,000 asylum applications per year, with fewer than 4% ultimately approved (Tramountanis, 2023). The system was also characterised by the non-proper transposition and implementation of EU Directives, the enhanced role of the police in decision-making, poor utilisation of available EU funds, limited administrative capacities, minimal and sporadic protective measures, excessive use of detention, and substandard living conditions in reception and detention facilities, among others (Black, 1994; Sitaropoulos, 2000; Papadopoulou, 2004; Papageorgiou, 2013). It is characteristic that in 2011, the European Court of Human Rights and the Court of Justice of the EU ruled that systemic deficiencies in the Greek asylum procedure violated the European Convention on Human Rights and EU law (Tramountanis, 2023). Before the so called 'refugee crisis', Greece had not yet established an asylum system able to respond to the existing needs. It is indicative that it was only in 2011 that the Greek Asylum Service (GAS) was established, while it started operating in 2013. In the following, we analyse how the newly established asylum system, the asylum laws, policies and institutional framework after 2015 have had an impact on the reproduction of irregularisation.

In 2015 Greece became one of the main entry point to Europe for nearly one million refugees and migrants. This –initially transit– movement was soon disrupted by the EU-Turkey Statement in March 2016, which –among others– was a return agreement under which migrants and asylum seekers with unfounded or inadmissible claims would be 'returned' from Greece to Turkey. While its implementation resulted in the decrease of departures from Turkey, it did not really increased the numbers of actual returns that remained very low in comparison with the number of arrivals. At the same time, other EU agreements with third countries were paving the way for deportations of specific nationals. Moreover, following the EU 'Hotspot Approach', five hotspots were established in the islands of Lesbos, Chios, Samos, Leros and Kos, while the Balkan Route was closed by March 2016. A Ministry of Migration Policy was established for the first time in Greece in 2016 (later MMA). Since then, extensive and substantial amendments of the Greek asylum law took place. As part of conforming to and implementing its obligations as a guardian of EU borders at the Union's south-eastern corner,

the asylum system was highly complex, constantly shifting, and adapting with mushrooming legislation (Tsitselikis, 2019)³.

5.1 Who deserves protection? Registration, complex asylum procedures and profiling

For a refugee⁴ in Greece, this labyrinth of irregularisation starts at the very beginning of the asylum process, especially during the registration of an asylum claim, or better, as part of **the procedure towards the registration**. On the one hand, those on the eastern border islands, are confronted with particular procedures deriving from the Hotspot Approach during their stay in the formerly Reception and Identification Centres (RICs), recently re-established as Closed Controlled Access Centres (CCACs). These may include their ad-hoc detention in the RICs or CCACs before registering their asylum claim, and their ‘geographical restriction of freedom of movement’ on the islands during the examination of their asylum application: both form spatial and carceral aspects of a process distinguishing those ‘deserving’ from those ‘undeserving’ protection and asylum. On the other hand, **those at the mainland who wish to register for asylum may end up irregularised** even if they should be considered as asylum seekers. Since September 2022, access to the asylum procedure on the mainland includes, first, the booking of an appointment through an online platform for the electronic pre-registration of asylum seekers and then the completion of the registration and the application in one of the two registration facilities in Diavata (Thessaloniki) or Malakasa (Attica). However, access to this has not always been possible, and in some cases, appointments for registration are assigned many months later. For example, some asylum seekers have waited over twelve months after initially applying for pre-registration before receiving an appointment (GCR-ECRE, 2023: 54). Moreover, in numerous cases, appointments were unavailable, underscoring the insufficient capacity of the facilities and resources. During this waiting period, applicants remain undocumented without access to reception provisions, medical care, or essential services, while they are not protected from detention (GCR-ECRE, 2023: 19-20).

‘There is also a part, before you go to the asylum procedure, if you have passed without ending up in a RIC or CCAC, hence you did not have access to asylum, then you have to make an appointment on a platform, appear in Malakasa (RIC), be subjected to de facto detention [...], and until you do all this you are in fact again in a limbo, even the document you get for your appointment does not give

³ To name but just a few, the main laws adopted since 2015 related to asylum, protection and reception of refugees are the Law 4375/2016 ‘Organisation and functioning of the Asylum Service, Appeals Authority, Reception and Identification Service, etc.’ and its amendments; Law 4540/2018 ‘Adaptation of Greek legislation to the provisions of Directive 2013/33/EU etc.’; Law 4636/2019 ‘on international protection and other provisions’ and its amendments; and Law 4939/2022 ‘Ratification of the Code on reception, international protection of TCNs and stateless persons, and on temporary protection in cases of mass influx of displaced migrants’ and its amendments.

⁴ In this paper, we avoid differentiating between the terms ‘migrant’, ‘refugee’, ‘asylum seeker’, etc., due to our understanding of the movement of refugees as a component of the broader migration phenomenon. The use of the term ‘asylum seekers’ is because it is the official designation used by the asylum system that we examine, and although conformist, the term highlights the tenuous distinction between migrants and refugees.

you any rights. You may be arrested while holding this document'
(GAPs_GRstakeholder13_2024).

As the above indicate, such long, complex and lengthy procedures lacking basic safeguards create frustration among refugees, disincentivise asylum applications functioning as a form of deterrence, and eventually push asylum seekers into different forms of irregularisation. As mentioned by a lawyer, representative of a Greek NGO, this development also indicates a policy of expelling refugees and the refugee issue from the public sphere and from visibility. It should be mentioned that before the adoption of this procedure (since 2014), access to the asylum procedure on the mainland took place through an appointment system via Skype, also characterised by structural difficulties. Its shortcomings were primarily due to its limited capacity and availability of interpretation services, as well as barriers hindering applicants' access to the internet. As a result, individuals seeking asylum often had to make numerous attempts over several months before successfully connecting to the Skype line to secure an appointment for the full registration of their application. This process exposed them to the risk of potential arrest and detention by the police, while they were denied the support typically offered to asylum seekers, notably access to reception provisions (GCR-ECRE, 2023: 53).

The labyrinth of irregularisation is reproduced through asylum procedures themselves, which have become too complex. Different procedures are defined in Law but amended several times during the last few years, making the system extremely complicated. These include: 1) the Regular procedure (which may be either a i) Prioritised examination for applications likely to be well-founded or made by vulnerable applicants, or a ii) fast-track processing which aims at accelerating the processing of specific caseloads as part of the regular procedure, without reducing procedural guarantees), 2) the Admissibility procedure, 3) the Border procedure (which includes two types, i) the 'normal border procedure' and ii) the 'fast-track border procedure', 4) the Accelerated procedure (which entails lower procedural safeguards, whether labelled as 'accelerated procedure' in national law or not.) among others (GCR-ECRE, 2023: 25).

Moreover, a number of other ad hoc procedures also exist, that in cases contradict the rule of Law, but affect refugees' experiences and may reproduce aspects of irregularisation. An indicative example emerged during the first years of the 'refugee crisis' and its management on the Aegean border islands. More particularly, since 2017 a 'pilot project' known as the 'Low-Profile Scheme' has been implemented in Lesbos, Kos and partly Leros (Leivaditi et al., 2020). The 'Low Profile Scheme' refers to a highly systematised and arbitrary practice of detention which is not legally defined in the legislation. Newcomers belonging to particular nationalities, whose country of origin has low recognition rates in the EU due to the safe country of origin concept (such as people from Algeria, Morocco, Egypt, sub-Saharan countries, the Sahel, Pakistan and Bangladesh), were immediately placed in administrative detention upon completion of reception and identification procedures and remained there for the entire asylum procedure (GCR, 2018). Another more recent example, as explained by a lawyer, representative of an NGO, is that a process that provides refugee status to particular groups without an asylum interview has been implemented on the CCACs on the islands since September 2023. The procedure is called 'prima facie' and concerns people from Sudan, Yemen, and Palestine who after registration receive refugee status only through their files, without the need to conduct an interview (GAPs_GRstakeholder13_2024). Such practices constitute ad hoc decisions of actors in the field, permitted through the asylum system, giving room for arbitrary decisions to be made, by thus reproducing and redefining different categories of people; those 'deserving' and the 'undeserving' asylum and protection, as

categories that are highly fluid and unstable and may irregularise particular groups or individuals in not always visible ways.

As the above indicate, the asylum laws, policies, regulations and the institutional framework as they have been established and transformed since 2015-2016, reproduce a labyrinth of irregularisation for refugees in Greece. What is crucial is that irregularisation is reproduced in all stages of an asylum application, as also discussed in the following sections. It forms part of the procedure towards the registration of the asylum claim, when asylum seekers encounter the discouraging temporalities of the asylum system and its carceral dimensions through their detention. It is also reproduced through the multiplicity of asylum procedures that refer to - and at the same time construct- different categories of people, mainly around the axes of deservingness/undeservingness. Categorisations such as refugees VS asylum seekers, have already given their place to a range of categories based on different criteria or concepts, i.e. the 'safe country of origin' division. Such procedures derive –not from the 'gaps' of the asylum system– but from its very core, and systematically irregularise people and discourage asylum applicants of their right to asylum.

5.2 Criminalising asylum seekers' practices by depriving them from reception provisions

After the EU-Turkey Statement, the Hotspot approach, and the closure of the Balkan route, people on the move have been obliged to stay in Greece and undergo asylum procedures, by that time as the only possible pathway of regular migration towards Europe (Papatzani et al., 2022a). This pathway constitutes –till today– an option giving access to the status of asylum seeker, regular in its legal basis, but with a range of obstacles related to people's movement, settlement, and integration trajectories in the country.

The most prominent example is the increasing number of regulations that concern asylum seekers' reception stage during the examination of their asylum claim. Asylum seekers are obliged to follow a number of rules during their asylum examination, otherwise the reception conditions they are entitled to, or other reception provisions they receive during their stay in camps may be reduced or even terminated. More particularly, according to Article 61 (1), (2), (3) and (4) of the Asylum Code, reception provisions may be reduced or -in exceptional and specifically justified cases- withdrawn, following a decision of the competent reception authority, where applicants: a) If provided with accommodation in the context of reception, abandon said accommodation without informing the competent administration or without permission, or abandon the geographical location of residence which has been determined for them in the case of the geographical restriction on the Aegean islands; b) Do not comply with the obligation to report personal information, such as address and employment contracts, or do not attend in person or do not respond to requests for information or do not attend, in the process of the examination of their application for international protection, a personal interview within the deadline set by the receiving and examining authorities; c) Have lodged a subsequent application (GCR-ECRE, 2023: 150). Secondly, the reception authority reduces material reception conditions if it determines that the applicant has not submitted an application for international protection promptly upon arrival in Greece without a valid reason. Thirdly, the reception authority may withdraw material reception conditions if it is found that the applicant has concealed financial resources, thereby unjustly benefiting from these conditions.

Moreover, in 2021, a new regulation was introduced for the newly established CCAC on the islands. This includes the possibility of terminating accommodation and withdrawing material reception if applicants are unjustifiably not identified during two consecutive regular census-verifications of the resident population, although no separate procedure is outlined for this. Such census-verifications are also implemented in mainland camps regularly, and asylum seekers that are absent may lose their accommodation places in the camp (Papatzani et al., 2022a).

Based on the above regulations, asylum seekers, even if usually are not in risk of return or detention as they are considered as a ‘regular’ category, they are not permitted to implement a number of practices related to mobility and settlement in the country, as the asylum system renders these practices ‘irregular’. As the Greek Council for Refugees has reported, between June and December 2020, material reception provisions were withdrawn for 4,957 individuals—2,964 of whom were residing in camps and 2,033 in the ESTIA accommodation scheme—following either status recognition or a second-instance negative decision (GCR-ECRE, 2023: 152).

Yet such ‘irregular’ practices may include asylum seekers’ trans-regional or trans-local movements between different reception facilities in the country, their absences for reasons of employment before the period of six months after which they are entitled to work ‘legally’, their movements between different places e.g. from the camps to the nearest cities in order to cover daily needs, or needs of health and education, or maintain networks and relationships, among others (Papatzani 2022a; 2022b). Nevertheless, the labyrinth of complex regulations and highly restrictive rules, mainly related to asylum seekers’ reception and accommodation, essentially **irregularises such everyday practices of asylum seekers**, as people with regular status, through a range of punitive measures (e.g. by withdrawing or reducing material reception services and provisions). It thus may reproduce processes of irregularisation even during the examination of an asylum claim, thus during people’s entitlement to asylum provisions and to ‘regularity’.

5.3 Safe third country inadmissibility & suspension of readmissions to Turkey

Among other aspects of the increasingly complex asylum system, the admissibility procedure mentioned above has acquired a crucial role in the last few years relating to processes of irregularisation emerging especially since 2015. Under Article 89 of the Asylum Code, an application can be considered inadmissible, among others, when the ‘safe third country’ concept is applied.

The examination of the safe third country concept in practice used to take place under the scope of the fast-track border procedure since 2016. More specifically, from 2014 until June 2021, it was applied to **Syrians who fell under the EU-Turkey Statement**, namely those who had entered Greece via the Greek Aegean islands and who were subject to a ‘geographical restriction of freedom of movement’. They were **eligible to a fast-track procedure examining their cases** and often resulting in the granting of refugee status⁵. This situation

⁵ This procedure also applied to those who formerly resided in Syria who could provide original documents such as passports, or who had been identified as Syrians/persons with a former residence in Syria within the scope of the Reception and Identification Procedure; provided that the EU-Turkey Statement and the fast-track border procedure did not apply in their case.

changed significantly after the Joint Ministerial Decision (JMD) 42799/2021⁶, designating Turkey as a safe third country for asylum applicants coming from Syria, Afghanistan, Somalia, Pakistan, and Bangladesh without providing any legal reasoning (GCR-ECRE, 2023: 83). As a result, applications for international protection lodged by persons of the aforementioned nationalities, this time **throughout the Greek territory (borders and mainland)** (and not only at the borders) are examined under the safe third country concept; they are now channelled into the admissibility procedure upon arrival, to assess whether Turkey is a safe third country and whether their cases are admissible and should be examined on the merits. Three out of the five nationalities mentioned in the JMD are those who are most often recognised as refugees in Greece. The following table presents the numbers of inadmissibility decisions issued in 2022 and 2023, including decisions based on the border procedure and the safe third country concept.

Table 1. Inadmissible Decisions in 1st & 2nd Instance, including those based on the border procedure and the safe third country concept

Inadmissible Decisions in 1st & 2nd Instance, including those based on the border procedure and the safe third country concept				
	first instance inadmissibility decisions	first instance based on the border procedure and the safe third country concept	second instance inadmissibility decisions	second instance based on the border procedure and the safe third country concept
2022	8,962	3,601	6,043	2,708
2023	8,901	3,454	5,030	1,237

Source: Ministry of Migration and Asylum, 2023, 2024, & authors’ elaboration

Contrary to Art. 38 (4) of the Asylum Procedure Directive, applicants are not provided with an in merits examination. The overwhelming majority of those decisions concerned the procedure on the mainland. Subsequent applications lodged following a final rejection of an application for international protection as inadmissible are channelled again into admissibility procedures and dismissed based on the safe third country concept or due to a lack of new elements.

“The adoption of a national list on the designation of Turkey as a “safe third country” for citizens of Afghanistan, Syria, Pakistan, Somalia and Bangladesh has led to the arbitrary rejection of numerous asylum applications as inadmissible. As a result of the EASO, the Asylum Service rejects the international protection applications of applicants from these five countries without examining their merits, i.e. the reasons why they left their countries’ (GAPs_GRstakeholder6_2023).

At the same time, readmissions to Turkey have been suspended since March 2020 as a result of geopolitical antagonisms between Greece and Turkey, manifested through the events in

⁶ Amended by JMD 485868/2021 and 734214/2022

Evros region, after which Greece suspended the registration of asylum applications for one month and foresaw immediate deportation for those entering the Greek territory, while Turkey declared the suspension of readmissions presumably due to the COVID-19 outbreak (RSA, 2020). The suspension of readmissions to Turkey has created a wide 'grey zone' and exposed thousands of applicants for international protection, including vulnerable persons, to a number of significant risks (Hatziprokopiou et al., 2024). Particularly, refugees whose applications have been/are rejected as inadmissible based on the 'safe third country' concept end up **in a state of legal limbo, exposed to a direct risk of destitution and detention**, without access to an in-merit examination of their application and without the possibility to lodge a subsequent asylum application (GCR-ECRE, 2023: 83). This also leads to the **exclusion of people from reception conditions**, resulting in no access to dignified living standards or to cater for their basic subsistence needs, including health care and food (GCR-ECRE, 2023: 130). Despite this, the Asylum Service continues not to apply Article 38(4) of the Procedural Directive to applicants whose application is examined on the admissibility under the safe country concept vis-a-vis Turkey. As stated repeatedly by the EU Commission, 'to the extent the applicant is not permitted to enter the territory of the safe third country, in particular if the underlying situation preventing entry persists since 2018 or 2020, the MS shall ensure, in accordance with the Asylum Procedures Directive, that access to a procedure is given to the applicant' (GCR-ECRE, 2023: 20-21).

'People whose asylum claim is rejected under the safe third country [...] And at the same time, since March '20, before the Common Ministerial Decision, Turkey does not accept anyone back, okay? The Directive says that these people should normally, if they can't be returned, should have access to a merits examination. [...] We are talking about refugees. Syria, Afghanistan, Somalia. [...] in Greece there is no [...] automatic procedure as required by the Directive, that (since) you cannot be returned, I will examine you on merits and you will be granted refugee status. [...] Yeah, so there were a lot of people who are Syrian citizens, who are refugees and they make an asylum claim in Greece, it is rejected, as unacceptable, and they are left in a legal limbo. And then they have to reapply, reapply for asylum to have their claim examined' (GAPs_GRstakeholder13_2024).

In October 2021 this situation changed drastically. An internal Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) of the Asylum Service, still in force, declared that asylum seekers of these nationalities that had crossed from Turkey **a year ago or more must be considered as not having a special link with Turkey or that, in any case, this link had been breached**. Subsequently, this was applied to the majority of cases examined on the Aegean islands, leading, eventually, to admissibility decisions and the examination of the asylum applications on their merits. Thus, several first instance decisions with the same reasoning have been issued since October 2021, since the aforementioned SOP started to be implemented. **This has been of great importance for all Syrian cases, and even Afghans and Somalis stuck in 'limbo' in Greece for more than a year**, many of whom were waiting for the examination of their subsequent applications.

'At some point in 2022, the Asylum Service said, [...] "if you've been in Greece for a year, then I don't consider you to have a connection with Turkey, so I consider your application admissible" [...] so in that one year, waiting for the one year to pass you are in limbo, so you are in limbo. Also, if you've made an asylum claim in this year e.g. you don't have proper legal advice, how would you know that

trick, that's a trick we're talking about. [...] but we end up saying to a person, "don't make an asylum claim yet, wait...". Yes, but if you make an asylum application and it is rejected because the year has not passed, for example, and you go to make a second subsequent one as soon as the year has passed, you have to pay a fee of one hundred euros. And if you're a family of six, it's 600 euros' (GAPs_GRstakeholder13_2024).

The above-mentioned 'trick', as one legal representative described it, managed to provide a temporary solution for people who were stuck in a legal limbo because their applications were deemed inadmissible due to the fact that Turkey was considered a safe third country, but at the same time they couldn't be returned to Turkey due to the suspension of readmissions. By waiting for a year, they could prove that they had no ties with Turkey, but during this 'waiting' they remained irregularised in Greece, without any rights. If they were lucky enough to have well-informed legal advice, they would be able to have their applications considered admissible after this one year - if not, they would have to make another application, paying a fee. The complex situation described above is only one of many that place refugees in a position of obligatory protracted irregularity, to be finally followed (after the late issuance of the authorities' decision) by the admissible examination of their asylum claim, which will hopefully lead to international protection at a later stage. In other words, when international protection is acquired, it follows a sequence of irregularity.

5.4 Irregularisation during processes of notification of decision and appeals

Aspects of irregularisation are also reproduced during processes of notification of the asylum decisions as well as processes of appeal. As regards the notifications of first instance decisions, it should be mentioned that the International Protection Act further introduced the possibility for decisions not to be communicated in person to the applicant ('fictitious service'/ *πλασματική επίδοση*) or to be communicated to the applicant by administrative authorities other than the Asylum Service. Both practices were maintained in the Asylum Code throughout 2022 and may significantly underestimate the possibility for the applicant to be informed about the issuance of the first instance decision and/or the content of this decision and/or the possibility to lodge an appeal. Consequently, deadlines for submitting an appeal against a negative first-instance decision may expire without the applicant being actually informed about the decision. As the Greek Ombudsman has noted with regard to the provisions of fictitious service, they effectively limit the access of asylum seekers to legal remedies (GCR-ECRE, 2023: 60). Concerning the notification of second instance decision, similar to the 'fictitious service' at first instance, both the International Protection Act and the Asylum Code also provide the possibility of a 'fictitious service' of second instance decisions as described above. Once again, as a result of this provision - which triggers the deadline for lodging an appeal - these deadlines for legal remedies against a negative second instance decision may expire without the applicant being actually informed about the decision (GCR-ECRE, 2023: 67-68). In other words, the applicants may remain irregularised without knowing it, and may lose their chance to appeal.

As far as appeals are concerned, first instance decisions of the Asylum Service are appealed before the Independent Appeals Committees under the Appeals Authority. Appeals before the Appeals Authority had automatic suspensive effect in all procedures under the previous law. The International Protection Act abolished the automatic suspensive effect for certain appeals,

in particular, those concerning applications rejected in the accelerated procedure or dismissed as inadmissible under certain grounds (GCR-ECRE, 2023: 65). The Asylum Code that came into force in the second half of 2022 has maintained these provisions. Thus, appeals submitted against decisions rejecting applications in the accelerated procedure or dismissed as inadmissible on certain grounds do not have an automatic suspensive effect despite the fact that these decisions also incorporate a return decision with immediate effect (GCR-ECRE, 2023: 20). In such cases, the appellant may submit an application before the Appeals Committees, requesting their stay in the country until the second-instance appeal decision is issued. However, considering the significant lack of an adequate system for the provision of free legal aid, it is questionable if such appellants will in fact be able to submit the relevant request. Suspensive effect covers the period during the time limit provided for an appeal and until the notification of the decision on the appeal (GCR-ECRE, 2023: 65).

According to the IPA, and regarding the process of judicial review, applicants for international protection may lodge an application for annulment of a second instance decision of the Appeals Authority Committees solely before the Administrative Court of First Instance of Athens or Thessaloniki within 30 days from the notification of the decision. According to the International Protection Act, following the lodging of the application for annulment, an application for suspension/interim order can be filed. The decision on this single application for temporary protection from removal should be issued within 15 days from the lodging of the application. The effectiveness of these legal remedies is severely undermined by a number of practical and legal obstacles, including – among others – that the application for annulment and application for suspension/interim order do not have automatic suspensive effect. Therefore between the application of suspension/interim order and the decision of the court, there is no guarantee that the applicant will not be removed from the territory (GCR-ECRE, 2023: 68-69).

Overall, the above legal provisions, as well as their particular implementation and the obstacles encountered tend to reproduce certain pathways to irregularisation, and at the same time do not protect from the risk of return or detention. The above remind what was earlier mentioned that irregularisation in Greece is reproduced in all stages of an asylum claim examination.

5.5 An ambiguous return framework of coercion that reinforces irregularisation

As Hatziprokiopou et al. (2024) recently noted, returns in Greece are governed by an ambiguous legal framework mainly due to preceding legal arrangements on ‘administrative expulsion’ that remain in force. More particularly, the co-existence of Law 3907/2011 which transposed the Return Directive 2008/115/EC into the Greek legislation and determines the operation of returns, and Law 3386/2005 regarding administrative expulsions of third country nationals in the Greek legal order seems to produce ambiguity regarding the respective scopes of the two laws. A number of inconsistencies emerge in this regard, including the fact that the state administration often bypasses the procedures of the Directive and apply the deportation procedures of Law 3386/2005 (Hatziprokiopou et al., 2024).

This is the case, for example, with expulsion decisions issued against TCNs illegally entering Greece at the borders even if the TCNs subsequently apply for international protection and obtain a permit to stay in the country; something that raises issues of compatibility with the Return Directive and the Return Handbook (European Commission, 2017). In Greece, TCNs irregularly entering Greece at the borders are arrested, detained and an expulsion decision is

issued against them in dereliction of the reception and identification process set out in Law 4939/2022 (art. 38). Additionally, CJEU has ruled that the term ‘in connection with the irregular crossing’ in Article 2(2)(a) of the Directive requires a ‘direct temporal and spatial link with that crossing of the border’. It thereby applies to persons ‘apprehended or intercepted by the competent authorities at the very time of the irregular crossing of the border or near that border after it has been so crossed’⁷. Subsequently, in the event that a TCN applies for international protection, s(he) obtains an authorisation to stay in the country and his/her expulsion is suspended until the completion of the examination of his/her application. If the application is rejected, the expulsion decision is executed in accordance with the procedures of Law 3386/2005. This procedure raises issues of compatibility with Article 2 para. (2) (a) of the Return Directive which clarifies that an exception from the scope of the Directive can only occur if TCNs who were caught irregularly crossing the border were not subsequently granted the right to remain in the country (National Commission for Human Rights, 2021).

‘The (Return) Directive sets a framework and explains when it is allowed an exception, derogation from the framework of the Directive [...] What has been observed over the last 7 years in the islands of the Eastern Aegean is that this derogation is being systematically used, but without the relevant conditions for the use of this derogation, i.e. there is no closely linked arrest of a person in the border. [...] The police systematically issues a deportation order to exist, which is often not delivered. [...] so that an administrative individual file can be opened and an administrative readmission procedure can be initiated. [...] This practice is doubly problematic because, on the one hand, a decision ordering an illegal removal (expulsion) is issued, since the asylum seeker is not expelled, while the asylum procedure is ongoing, on the basis of the principle of non-refoulement, and, on the other hand, it is issued with the wrong procedure because it does not legally derogate from the Return Directive’ (GAPs_GRstakeholder6_2023).

Another type of irregularisation may emerge even during the assisted ‘voluntary’ returns from Greece, and particularly the Assisted Voluntary Return and Re-integration Programme (AVRR), implemented by the International Organization for Migration (IOM). While participation in AVRR is voluntary in the sense that any participant has the right to withdraw at any time, the wider context in which the program operates is one of coercion (Hatziprokopiou et al., 2024). Other scholars also argue about the character of AVRR program as a project of ‘self-deportation’ (Spathopoulou et al., 2022). This is because AVRR is also addressed to migrants issued with a return decision and even detainees and thus, it risks being a ‘facade’ of ‘voluntariness’ for migrants who face ‘the tough dilemma of absconding or departing “voluntarily”’ (Triandafyllidou & Ricard-Guay, 2019). Besides, the interplay of formal polices and informal practices in returns may reveal the nuances in the forced and voluntary return dichotomy, and more importantly the coerced nature even of the ‘voluntary’ procedures (Sahin-Mencutek & Triandafyllidou, forthcoming). Furthermore, there exist relations between AVRR and detention, as IOM’s practices include close interventions and communication in detention centers, as people registered in AVRR may also be kept in detention. On the one hand, this applies to those who register for AVRR while in detention and remain detained despite their declared willingness and consent to return. On the other hand, it may also apply to those who register in AVRR while at liberty but get arrested by the police

⁷ CJEU, Case C-47/15 Affum b Préfet du Pas-de-Calais and Procureur général de la Cour d'appel de Douai, 7 June 2016, para 72; Case C-444/17 Arib, 19 March 2019, para 46.

afterwards and are held in detention, again despite that AVRR procedures have already started (Hatziprokopiou et al., 2024).

Even more crucially, registration in the AVRR involves an implicit coercion leading to the acceptance of an irregular status, as enrolment in the program and its provisions presupposes that the migrants should abandon or withdraw their efforts on asylum applications, to refrain from any rights coming with a regular status – either of an asylum seeker or of an international protection beneficiary or a migrant on a valid stay permit – and remain in an irregular status for a few days before applying for return.

‘The whole part of the returns is based on the free will of the person [...] Even a recognised person, a migrant who has received international protection, can give up his status if he wants to, and go through the process normally. [...] Then there is the case of a person coming to us, being an asylum seeker here, that is, with an active asylum claim, but wishing to leave. In that case, the resignation procedure should be promoted, i.e. the person should give up the asylum, so that the resignation can act as a decision to return. Again, it is done with a referral from us in cooperation with the asylum service, an appointment is made and the person can go to the asylum service and withdraw from the asylum claim’ (GAPs_GRstakeholder1_2023).

What the above reveal is that irregularisation is directly reproduced by the legal and institutional framework of governing returns in Greece. This framework allows the authorities to employ detention and deportation procedures even for people who claim asylum immediately. In parallel, in the case of ‘voluntary’ assisted returns, questions of coercion arise (Sahin-Mencutek et al., 2023; Sahin-Mencutek & Triandafyllidou, forthcoming), in an otherwise self-proclaimed ‘voluntary’ program based on the free will of people and their informed decision.

5.6 Irregularisation as process: The stories data (don’t) tell

In the previous sections we showed how irregularisation is (re)produced in Greece through the immigration policy framework and asylum system, focusing on specific procedures and practices within the latter as evolved since 2015 and especially considering recent developments. The complexity of pathways to and from (ir)regularity as well the ambiguity, fluidity and hence precarity of status unveiled a rather messy situation in sharp contrast with the clear-cut on/off or either/or categories of documented vs illegal that politicians like to portray and that official statistics often imply. For example, the structure of Eurostat data under the topic ‘Enforcement of immigration legislation’ (EIL) consists of four sub-topics: refusal of entry at the external (Schengen) border; individuals found to be illegally present in the territory of a Member State (MS); individuals ordered to leave a MS (not including those transferred to another MS under the Dublin mechanism); and those who ‘returned’, i.e. left a MS following an order to leave (Eurostat 2022)⁸.

This is a structure apparently suitable for two connected purposes. The first is to evaluate and assess law enforcement, especially by comparing the number of those returning to the larger pool of those ordered to leave and the even larger of those illegally present. The second is to

⁸ Also see Reference Metadata at:

[https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/migr_eil_esms.htm]. Accessed: July 14, 2024.

create the impression that irregularity, albeit being by definition a difficult to measure phenomenon, is supposedly captured and monitored by official statistics. In other words, official statistics tend to shrink the complex process of irregularity/irregularisation into a simplistic linear succession of apprehension – order to leave – return. Paradoxically, detention statistics are not included, despite that detention is a key element of legislation enforcement, at least in the Return Directive (2008/115/EC). Similarly, there is no data about how many migrants were stopped by law enforcement agencies for the purpose of checking their documents and *not* found to be illegally present.

According to Eurostat data, the number of ‘TCNs found to be illegally present’ in Greece ranged from approximately 40,000 to slightly over 100,000 for most of the period from 2008 to 2023, with one notable exception in 2015-2016, years of the so-called ‘refugee crisis’ (Figure 1, blue line). Available data for past three years 2021-2023 reveal that the distribution between those who were apprehended in border regions and those apprehended in the inland is roughly equal, albeit showing some yearly fluctuation (Figure 1, yellow/red bars). As for the reason for apprehension, the vast majority of the cases are officially recorded by Eurostat as ‘illegal entry’ and only a few hundred each year as ‘overstay’. Obviously, this means that numerous migrants are apprehended for illegal entry in places of the inland practically unconnected with official or unofficial entry points at the borders.

Figure 1: Number of TCNs found to be illegally present in Greece, 2008-2023

Source: Eurostat database [migr_eipre]

The number of TCNs ordered to leave showed a sharp increase after 2015 and then decline over 2020-23, with an exception in 2022, following a relatively parallel trend with the data described above (Figure 2). At the same time, the number of those who returned following an order represents a steady minority only of those receiving such an order. Moreover, an overview of the main nationalities of the individuals who were identified as illegally present between 2016 and 2023 shows that seven out of ten were citizens of five countries: Syria comes first (with 25%) and is followed by Afghanistan (17%), Albania (11%), Iraq (10%) and Pakistan (10%). The same countries figure in the top of the list of those receiving a return decision, but in a different order: Albania (17%), Pakistan (17%), Syria (12%), Afghanistan (10%) and Iraq (8%). Concerning migrants who did ‘return’ to another country during the same period, either by a forced return operation, an assisted ‘voluntary’ return operation or as non-assisted, the main countries of citizenship include Albania which comes first with 51%, Pakistan (11%), Georgia (10%), Iraq (7%), and Afghanistan (3%), but returns to the country have effectively ceased since 2022).

Figure 2: Number of TCNs found illegally present, ordered to leave and returned, Greece 2016-2023 (rounded)

Source: Eurostat database [migr_eipre], [migr_eiord], [migr_eirtn].

There are two main conclusions that derive from these statistics. First, Albanians, by far the biggest migrant group in the country and a long-established one, also constitute the biggest group of those returned from Greece to their country of origin. Despite that most ‘irregular’ Albanians are apprehended for illegal entry in Greece, they mainly get arrested in inland areas. We may reasonably assume that at least a number of them and subsequently of those returning are not newcomers, but people who have lived for longer or shorter periods in Greece, possibly moving ‘back’ and ‘forth’ between Greece and Albania, albeit not being able to get and/or renew a legal migrant status⁹. Second, several other third country nationals continue to be identified as ‘illegally present’ and subsequently ordered to leave, despite being citizens of countries where return is practically impossible, for whom high levels of recognition as beneficiaries of international protection are recorded. Apart from Syrians and Afghans, this also applies to migrants from smaller communities in Greece, such as Palestinians and Iranians. Thus, irregularity can be seen as a condition that affects various migrant groups, either those with members that have longer presence in the country and have experienced previous and current periods of legal stay, or those with members who face life conditions directly linked to what international rules determine as refugee status.

The national system for collecting and processing EIL-statistics starts with the Regional Services of the Hellenic Police which register data in an application called ‘Mapping of Migrants’. Two centralised police agencies, namely the Border Protection Division and the Migration Management Division are responsible to ‘receive’ and ‘extract’ data from this application and then to ‘fill into Eurostat’s template’ and ‘validate the results’. Despite that there is no external validation and data quality assessment mechanism, the related National Reference Metadata published by Eurostat¹⁰ reports no accuracy issues. However, beyond the quality of data as such, the procedures followed by the Hellenic Police and other collaborating

⁹ Eurostat data remain silent about the period of stay or the date of arrival of the apprehended and the ‘returned’ in a MS. Failing to collect such information, individual trajectories prior to apprehension or return are effectively effaced.

¹⁰ See [https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/EN/migr_eil_esqrs_el.htm]. Accessed: 14 July 2024.

agencies while enforcing the immigration legislation are out of the question for the National Reference Metadata – similarly as in the case of other aspects of institutional practices producing irregularisation shown in this chapter.

Furthermore, migrants' trajectories often follow paths that fall beyond the scope of the clear-cut categories and sequential stages unfolding in the linear way as the data imply. As mentioned earlier, applying for asylum in Greece is one of the few possible regular migration pathways towards Europe. Nevertheless, as we have shown, the asylum process entails multiple aspects of irregularisation, even in cases of regular status, e.g. that of the asylum seeker. At the same time, the hardships that asylum seekers encounter in Greece affect future mobilities and decisions. It is not rare, for example, asylum seekers, or beneficiaries of international protection to decide to irregularly leave Greece towards other European countries where circumstances are better. Most usually complete the asylum process and attempt to reach their desired destinations once they receive international protection status in Greece, yet there are some who leave Greece before completing the process (Papatzani et al., 2022a). This practice results in irregularity in their new destinations, as asylum seekers in Greece will have to confront the Dublin Regulation on the 'first country of asylum' and the implications it may bring, while recognised refugees are allowed to travel to other EU countries for three-month visits only. Despite this, there exist institutional pathways permitting refugees recognised in Greece to settle in other EU countries, on the grounds of harsh living conditions and limited integration prospects; these include a number of courts' decisions in line with the 2011 judgment *M.S.S. v. Belgium and Greece* that did not permit refugees recognised in Greece to be returned¹¹.

At the same time, the labyrinthine asylum system and the strict and complex policies and procedures that are meant to deterrence may lead people on the move to **decide not to apply for asylum in Greece and skip entirely the system from the very beginning**, by trying to avoid being arrested and fingerprinted at the borders or in mainland Greece (Papatzani et al., 2022a). In other words, some migrants may choose to remain **self-irregularised** during their short stay in Greece, while making arrangements for their next mobility steps, and remain undocumented in different areas in the country, usually the large urban centers, while their everyday life mainly involves a continuous search for ways to leave Greece. As undocumented, they are constantly under the fear and threat of arrest by the regular police controls on the streets, which could lead to their detention and deportation from Greece. This is why, as research has shown in the case of Athens, they usually avoid spending time in public, they use to hide from the police, change their routes during their everyday mobilities, thus living in the shadows of the city even if at the same time residing at its very center (Papatzani, 2021).

¹¹ e.g. <https://www.courthousenews.com/refugees-cannot-be-returned-to-greece-german-court-rules>

6. Intersecting Layers of Irregularisation

6.1 Temporal

Conceptualising irregularisation as a process implies a temporal layer. As evidenced throughout chapter 5, for various normatively defined categories of migrants, the Greek migration regime is characterised by different stages and sequences, diverging paces and tempos, timeframes and deadlines, durations and temporalities as well as temporal inconsistencies. This section brings to the fore some of the temporal dimensions in processes of irregularisation stemming from the legal framework, administrative procedures and their implementation in practice that have already been discussed in the previous chapter. Moreover, it situates these in a historical overview of how Greek migration and asylum policies have evolved over time.

Irregularity may be a product of the law, but it begins at the borders even before they are crossed. The observation by van Liempt et al. (2023: 4) that ‘in the 21st century, irregularity is inherently related to the lack of legal migration channels’ holds true in our case. Indeed, the vast majority of newly arriving migrants enter the country without authorisation, mainly due to the unavailability of alternative (legal) routes. This may paradoxically bare similarities with the early 1990s, i.e. when Greece first emerged as a destination and most migrants arrived by irregularly crossing the border due to the virtually absent provisions for regular entry (and stay). Even when legal pathways to regularisation came by, in the late 1990s, these proved to be complicated in practice, due to the spirit of these measures but also their administrative handling (Hatziprokiou, 2006), and were marked by several temporalities: stages, overlaps and setbacks, waiting, time inconsistencies.

A first ‘amnesty’ programme, for example, initiated in 1998, involved two stages: people would receive a temporary permit at a first place before being able to apply for a stay permit of longer duration; but tight criteria including proof of regular employment had deterred many from passing on to the second stage. This is why the applicants in subsequent large-scale regularisation programmes (2001, 2005) partly overlapped, either because a previous application was rejected, or because criteria for renewal were impossible to meet (Triandafyllidou, 2014). Long queues of people waiting to submit applications or receive documents from various authorities were common, sometimes resulting in casualties that have never been investigated (Kandylis, Papatzani, Polyzos, forthcoming). The short duration of most stay permits, coupled with administrative deficiencies such as severe delays in the issuing or renewal of a permit would often result in the absurd situation of receiving the documents after they had expired (Hatziprokiou, 2006). In the meanwhile, short-sighted planning had resulted in legal gaps that left certain categories of people with migrant background in a limbo, again involving temporal layers entailing setbacks to irregularity. Coming of age is an example: when the children of immigrants would reach adulthood, they lost their status as dependents covered by their parents’ stay permit. In the lack of provisions specific to them, applying for a stay permit often led to bureaucratic absurdities such as being asked to submit a birth certificate from their parents’ country of origin even if the applicants were born in Greece¹².

¹² An amendment to the Citizenship Law 3838/2010 came to provide a relatively easy path to citizenship for children born or schooled in Greece, yet this was later annulled by the Council of State, before being partly reinstated through provisions for a special ‘second generation’ permit (Law 4251/2014) and subsequent measures facilitating access to citizenship (Law 4332/2015). The recent Immigration Code (Law 5038/2023) has been criticised for reintroducing difficulties for some categories of children born

Figure 3: Valid resident permits in Greece, 2016-2023

Source: Ministry of Migration and Asylum, Authors' elaboration

Even though many long-settled migrants are now holders of long term or indefinite duration stay permits, precarity remains order of the day. A look at stay permit statistics over time reveals high fluctuations in the numbers of legally residing migrants (see Figure 3): a significant growth of about 185,000 valid permits between 2020 and 2021 was followed by substantial decrease of more than 221,000 permits by the end of 2022. This may be partly explained by increased numbers of stay permit applications that the bureaucracy falls short to process: between 2021 and 2022 the number of applications for new permits grew by 47%, while those for renewals grew by 40%; within 2023, alone more than 121,000 applications for new permits were launched, more than double the number of 2022. As a result, there has been a rise of applications pending to be examined for both new stay permits and renewals: respectively 87,358 and 83,747 at the end of 2023. The point implied here has to do with the repercussions in the lives of the people concerned, revealing recurring patterns of lasting legal ambiguity for significant numbers of migrants. What is more, different types of stay permit expectedly are of different durations. Stay permits for dependent employment last for relatively short periods of time, while permits for seasonal work e.g. in agriculture give access to the Greek labour market for up to 9 months annually for a total period of up to 5 years. The aforementioned 'Memorandum of Understanding' signed in 2022 with Bangladesh (see chapter 4) had similar provisions. Similar timeframes are set in the ongoing larger scale regularisation giving access to a 3-year residence permit for employment to migrants who can prove three years continuous stay in Greece.

As mentioned earlier, even before 2015 asylum has long been a main 'corridor' for many migrants heading to Europe: asylum claimants in the 2000s would receive an application certificate (the so-called 'pink card') which would grant them temporary status, albeit precarious, though giving time to regularise their status or attempt onward movement (Papadopoulou, 2004; Christopoulos, 2020). To some extent this went on after establishing competent bodies, and continued, in the absence of any provisions for alternative pathways to regular entry, or safe passages for refugees, albeit in different ways amidst tightening border

or schooled in Greece who reach adulthood, as they can only be granted a stay permit provided they were holders of a different type of stay permit as minors.

controls, increasing restrictions and mushrooming legislation following the ‘long summer of migration’, as already documented in detail.

Registering for asylum involves multiple stages, temporalities and waiting periods. Registration at the border involves a period of confinement on the islands, often starting with ad hoc detention (see below) followed by stay in a RIC (or more recently a CCAC). Lately this is set to last for no more than 25 days, at least on paper. In cases of people who have crossed a land border or have otherwise managed to somehow bypass the island-based “hotspots” may involve much longer waits (over 12 months) between the moment of (online) pre-registration and the actual timing of a registration appointment, while in the meanwhile applicants remain in practice undocumented, without having access to reception provisions or services, neither protection from detention (GCR-ECRE, 2023: 19-20).

At the implementation level, however, there are diversions from the Law. For example, since 2016, for every new arrival ‘the Greek police systematically issues a deportation decision involving the newcomer’s detention, with the aim of readmission to Turkey’. This was noted by one of our expert interviews (GAPs_GRstakeholder6_2023), who explained that the police does so by invoking the provisions of Law 3386/2005 on deportation as well as Law 3907/2011 yet on derogation from the Directive; even if this is rarely implemented, it serves ‘to open an administrative individual file and to be able to initiate an administrative readmission process’. All too often, no time difference is stated on the document ‘between the arrival and the issuing of the decision’. Yet, in many cases, the decision is not handed to the persons concerned, hence they are not aware that there’s a deportation decision which comes before all other procedures that follow.

The asylum procedure itself, as earlier detailed, is characterised by different tempos and varying paces: prioritised or fast-track *regular* procedure, fast-track *border* procedure, *accelerated* procedure. Moreover, expectedly as it may be in any bureaucratic system, different phases and steps in the asylum procedure involve specific timeframes, as well as tight deadlines. For instance, the MMA website informs asylum claimants: that their application may take between 2- days to six months to be processed; that, in case of a negative decision, an appeal must be lodged within a deadline specified in the decision; that, if granted Geneva refugee status, their Uniform-Format Residence Permit (ADET) is valid for three years and can be renewed by applying via e-mail no later than 30 calendar days expiry; and many more. Failure to meet deadlines in these cases does not deprive refugees from their rights, but involves expensive penalty fees.

However, such prescribed timeframes do not always work in practice, thus subjecting migrants and asylum seekers to further precarity and irregularisation. As mentioned, until recently, long periods of waiting and uncertainty (for an asylum decision, of staying in a camp, etc.) were followed by periods marked accelerated speed to meet several tight deadlines to complete several formalities. As we have seen in section 5.6, there have been cases of asylum seekers bypassing the reception system in order to move on with their lives and join family or other social networks elsewhere in the country (Papatzani et al., 2022a). This was of course before recent legal amendments which have increased punitive restrictions involving penalties, such as losing benefits or even revoking the asylum application (section 5.2). Moreover, when the ‘safe third country’ concept was initially introduced in legislation for specific nationalities (section 5.3), it was retrospectively applied for people who had been already waiting in a camp for an outcome on their asylum applications, which risked being revoked.

Further, deadlines for submitting an appeal against a negative first-instance decision may expire without the applicant being actually informed about the decision (section 5.4). Whether following a negative first instance decision or the outcome of an appeal, migrants receive an

order to willingly leave the country within a set period of time (subject to extension). However, not all migrants comply with this order, for a number of reasons. In a recent paper, Tsavdaroglou et al. (2024: 2) narrate the story of one of their interlocutors in Thessaloniki, a migrant from Algeria who crossed through Turkey in 2017: after spending two years in a camp, he received a negative decision, stayed homeless and undocumented before seeking ‘refuge, like many other migrants without papers or unregistered newcomers, to the abandoned train wagon areas in the western part of the city’. Going invisible and ‘under the radar’, however, as discussed in 5.6, may appear as a reasonable option for desperate asylum seekers who are separated from close family members and are tired of waiting for an asylum decision. Papatzani et al (2022a: 4396) recall the experience of a young Afghan woman who, at the time of her interview in 2020, resided in a subsidised (ESTIA) apartment in Athens after having lived in a Lesvos hotspot and a camp in Attica since her arrival in 2016, still waiting for her asylum interview. She was determined to follow her parents and siblings to join a sister in Germany, even if that meant traveling irregularly: ‘No, I don't want to wait for that... I have a plan to go, informally... There is no other choice’. The authors observe that ‘the boundaries between different mobility types are blurred and porous, as are the sequences of “legal” or ‘irregular’ statuses to which they lead and with which they closely interrelate’, concluding that ‘if ‘legality’ – that is, going through the Greek asylum system – entails multiple layers of immobilisation, then moving at the margins, bypassing restrictions, or opting out of the system may facilitate mobility in multiple scales, local or transnational, albeit unauthorized’ (Papatzani et al., 2022a: 4396).

6.2 Spatial

As evidenced in the previous chapter, the labyrinth of irregularisation procedures has its own equally labyrinthine spatiality. We could argue that irregularisation is an inherently geographical process that starts before border-crossing and entails diverse routes along which legislation and institutional practices categorise people and places (and emplaced people for that matter). Geography can be detrimental throughout the asylum process, impacting at the assessment of asylum applications as well as on the treatment of all the categories of migrants. Expectedly, the spatiality of irregularisation involves national borders but not only as lines that separate states. As has been discussed in an already vast but still burgeoning literature in border studies inspired especially by migration ethnographies borders may and do extend beyond border zones, both externalising outside and internalising within the nation-state (e.g. Parker et al., 2009; Mekdjian, 2015; Chattopadhyay, 2019; Fauser, 2024).

To begin with, migrants’ nationality determines in multiple ways their access to asylum and the outcome of their claims. In 2015 SIA (Syrian, Iraqi, Afghan) was a shortcode implying the faster and relatively easier access to the asylum process by nationals of these countries. Gradually, this relative ease was attributed solely to Syrians and more recently, not even to them as discussions about ‘returning’ Syrian refugees to safe areas there thrived recently. This is further reflected in the newer procedures (especially the border one) where migrants coming from countries with lower than 20% recognition rate will be directed to.

The route that migrants follow in order to reach Greece / the EU is also impacted by EU border control policies, including Frontex operations. This means migrants being directed to more dangerous crossings in order to avoid being apprehended, being more dependent on the traffickers and the information they provide and often finding themselves in highly vulnerable and risky situations before and during crossings; situations that clearly result in their multiple irregularisation. But even when they have reached or are about to reach the borders, migrants

might find themselves in the midst of state's (and implicitly EU's) illegal and informal practices of pushbacks. Numerous reports have traced and described the processes and often deadly outcomes of pushbacks. Even when not deadly, pushbacks pull migrants into yet another cycle of irregularisation and obstruction of filing an asylum application. If people escape being pushed back, when they are arrested at the borders, they immediately have a deportation order filed for them – even if it's not executed due to the filing of an asylum claim. As this is not something communicated with those arrested, people might find themselves into an irregular status while in Greece without even knowing it.

As several of our experts / interviewees pointed out, at present, there are minimal chances that a migrant can file an asylum application without being detained either during the identification process or as a result of the apprehension and arrest. Detention, along with the transformation of camps into 'Closed control access centres' create (carceral) zones of waiting and uncertainty at or close Greece's eastern (mostly) borders. In line to observations of several researchers, the border and the irregularisation it imposes is encountered not only at a country's territorial edges but also within.

Moreover, the assemblage of spatial entities involved in 'reception and identification', accommodation and return processes at times blurs the boundaries of (il)legal, (ir)regular, registered, detained, to-be-returned, deportee, asylum-seeker further. This assemblage consists of RICs, CCACs) which contain RICs and detention and/or pre-deportation facilities, Controlled Access Facilities of Temporary Accommodation (previously called *Open* Facilities), and Pre-Removal Detention Centers (PRDCs). The geography of these facilities extends to the Eastern border of Greece (Lesvos, Chios, Samos, Leros, Kos, Evros) plus Attica (Malakasa), Thessaloniki (Diavata) and the outskirts of smaller cities. Within these, people may acquire changing statuses and spectrums of (il)legalisation as they are transferred from one space to another. The aforementioned registration identification and return infrastructures / assemblage are also coupled with PRDCs, managed by the Greek police, at Korinth, Athens, Drama, Fylakio and Xanthi, as well as with police cells who operate as pre-departure 'facilities' (see Greek Ombudsman, 2023: 23).

The 'typical' process states that after identification TCs are transferred to inland facilities in order to either file and be assessed as recipients of international and subsidiary protection or to be re-admitted (to Turkey), returned or deported. Yet 'typical' often becomes rather un-typical in the way the whole processes unfold. As one of our experts explains:

There is an explicit obligation for the police/coast guard, as soon as they come into contact with a person who does not have the legal documentation, to take him/her to a RIC/CCAC to start the identification process. In practice this does not happen: on the islands they can be transferred to the RIC/CCAC, but if someone is arrested without papers in the centre of Athens the same thing will not happen, they will be transferred for detention to a police station and then to a PROKEKA (detention center) (e.g. Amygdaleza), while there is a RIC in the mainland, e.g. in Malakasa. In other cases, although new arrivals on the islands have been subject to a reception/identification procedure and have applied for asylum, a deportation order is issued against them, which is not served, but exists even though the asylum seeker is not deportable' (GAPs_GRstakeholder6_2023).

For a significant period of time, the enforcement of geographic restrictions from 2016 onwards trapped people in the islands leaving scant options for being transferred to inland facilities. Furthermore, as of 2020 re-admissions to Turkey (in line with the EU-Turkey

statement) have been suspended, leading to an increase of people ‘incarcerated’, detained for long periods of time as their future was ‘pending’.

Last but not least, as already mentioned in the previous section, the designation of safe third countries (Albania, North Macedonia and Turkey for Syrian, Afghan, Pakistan, Bangladesh and Somali nationals) as well as of safe countries of origin (Egypt, Nepal, Benin, Ghana, Senegal, Togo, Gambia, Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Albania, Georgia, India, Armenia, Pakistan, Bangladesh and Ukraine (?)) have strongly and adversely impacted the whole asylum (and return) process by ‘fast-tracking’ re-admissions and returns and by rejecting asylum-claims. As a result, migrants spend increasing periods of time in legal limbo (waiting for appeals, etc.) as well as in spatial and temporal limbo as re-admissions and/or return operations might not be feasible (interview₁₃) and, in practice, are transformed into indefinite detention.

‘We officially know that the Afghans from 2021 onwards, because we sent a question to the headquarters of the Greek Police, that they are not being returned. And this has to do with the Taliban taking power. However, the single male Afghans, up to the end of 2022, continued to be detained in Greece for extended periods of time. This was a completely illegal detention. To our opinion, it was purely a means of discouragement and deterrence and of new entry. The idea was that we would give the message that we, here, are detaining the Afghans, which is completely stupid. I mean, we overestimate the deterrent power of detention. As if, they won't leave Afghanistan or Turkey to come here because we're going to detain them’ (GAPs_GRstakeholder₁₃_2024).

Interestingly, the variability of border procedures seems to be further institutionalised in the EU’s new Pact on Migration and Asylum (2024). Especially the Screening Regulation with its border procedure and accelerated procedures form a very restrictive (legally, temporally, spatially and subjectively) framework for assessing the ‘right’ to asylum and for distinguishing the ‘real’ from the ‘bogus’ (namely economically/poverty driven) refugees. Specifically, ‘people who “pose a security risk, who mislead the authorities by providing false information or withhold information, or who are coming from countries with a low recognition rate’ will be subjected to a ‘border procedure’ with the result that they will not remain at liberty in the country while their claim is being examined, but be obliged to remain at specific facilities at or near the border, for a maximum period of 12 weeks until it is decided whether they will move on to the ‘in-territory’ asylum procedure –the normal asylum procedure– or to expulsion (González Enríquez, 2024). The accelerated screening process is supposed to take place within seven days, deciding upon whether the person should be transferred to the traditional asylum procedure, be returned or go through the border procedure.

Detention, especially at the borders and nearby areas, becomes the de facto material and institutional way of ‘managing asylum’, since ‘the border procedure will often take place in detention, as will the new “pre-entry” screening process’ (Woollard, 2024). Both the screening process and the accelerated border procedure as well as the expansion of the use of detention, are founded on the legal method of ‘fiction of non-entry’. The ‘fiction of non-entry’ maintains that although a person is physically on the territory of a MS, legally his/her arrival at EU territory is not recognised as such thus placing her/him in a gray/limbo/transit zone (Woollard, 2024; Schug, 2024; González Enríquez, 2024). Woollard (2024) argues that both for border and accelerated procedures (which can be cumulative) ‘the pretence of non-entry applies, even when they take place away from the border, elsewhere on the territory, which is allowed’. Statewatch (2024) contends that the fiction of non-entry leads to lower safeguards and heightens the risk of human rights violations and pushbacks at borders.

6.3 Carceral

The link between return and detention is quite straightforward in the EU Return Directive (2008/15/EC), which set up ‘common standards and procedures for returning illegally staying third-country nationals’. In it, detention is prescribed as a means ‘to prepare the return and/or carry out the removal process’ of those who are ‘subject to return’, namely those who do not fulfil the Schengen conditions or other conditions for entry and stay in a MS. Thus, the Directive seems to imagine a linear procedure starting from illegal entry or stay and leading in turn to identification to a return decision to detention to removal. It is commonplace to remark that things are much more complicated during law implementation than on paper. What we further argue here is that implementation procedures work in a somewhat inverse trajectory, one in which the intention to remove migrants is the starting point and illegality is the ongoing outcome.

The Directive stipulates more precisely that detention is implemented when there is a risk of absconding or a TCN avoids or hampers the return process. To these already general reasons for detention the Greek law that transposed the Directive (Law 3907/2011) adds one more, that of national security concerns. In practice, detention is the rule rather than the exception whenever a return or expulsion decision is issued in Greece and, as the Greek Ombudsman has repeatedly observed, detention decisions are very often based on public security and public order reasons, pertaining to sentences for the possession of forged documents or non-possession of documents (Greek Ombudsman, 2019). As a result, third country nationals end up being detained for the sole reason of entering the country.

Migrants’ detention in Greece comes indeed very early after border crossing. First of all, the rule is that all newcomers have to be transferred by the police to one of the RICs or CCACs, where they are immediately deprived of their liberty for a period of up to 25 days for reasons of identification or screening. Since this is a general measure of detention practically applied to all newcomers, it seems to violate the EU Directive on reception standards for applicants of international protection (2013/33/EU) that stipulates that no one should be detained for the sole reason of being an applicant for international protection. Despite that it is generally known (and admitted by the authorities, see RSA, 2024) that most people in these facilities do apply for international protection, in practice this period of initial detention is imposed on everyone, no matter their individual circumstances and intention to submit an application.

‘The European Commission has initiated an infringement procedure for this [...]. What we have in our legislation allows us to detain anyone without pointing to the reasons, without justifying. The infringement procedure means that you have transposed the EU legislation in the wrong way, that you have a legislation that permits something not permitted by the EU law’ (GAPs_GRstakeholder6_2023).

Even individuals who have expressed their intention to apply for international protection via the devoted digital platform of MMA are detained for the same period of 25 days as soon as they arrive at the RICs in the mainland (GAPs interviews, Stakeholder 13). Both in RICs and in CCACs, migrants have reportedly been detained for a ‘waiting period’ even before their registration (and the 25 days) started.

‘Technically speaking (...) people who wish to apply for asylum in Greece have to put themselves in a status of deprivation of liberty. You cannot apply for asylum while at liberty in Greece’ GAPs_GRstakeholder6_2023.

Another layer of even earlier resort to detention has been introduced since 2016 and the infamous EU-Turkey Statement. During the period of its partial implementation, but also after its freezing by Turkey in 2020, the Hellenic Police continuously invoke the Statement in order to issue decisions of deportation accompanied by detention as soon as they encounter newcomers, for the purpose of readmission to Turkey. Interestingly, this procedure is officially applied in derogation from the Return Directive and based on the older Law 3386/2005.

In some cases, these decisions concern individuals who have declared their intention to apply for international protection (GAPs interview, Stakeholder 6). But even when an application for international protection is not finally submitted, this practice is legally contested since it affects people who are not arrested at the borders but in other areas, even several days after border crossing. Moreover, it is quite common for these readmission decisions not to be handed to those affected. On the other hand, undocumented migrants who are not arrested in the (sea or land) border regions but are caught for the first time in the mainland are not transferred to RICs but immediately held in detention in police stations and in the PRDCs.

Additionally, individuals who have already applied for international protection may be detained even after their application. This practice is grounded in the Reception Conditions Directive (2013/33/EU) which includes a list of reasons for detention, based on individual assessment. As Falsone (2021) remarks, in 2018 one in four applicants had been detained. Asylum seekers in Greece are not necessarily detained in separate facilities. They may be detained in PRDCs together with non-applicants, also in violation of the related provision of the Directive. In all these cases, it becomes quite evident that *de jure* or *de facto* detention is a generalised measure by which the Greek authorities communicate to newcomers that their arrival is irregular and that they should preferably comply to leave the country from the very first moment.

However, not only newcomers are exposed to the risk of detention. Established migrants also face various challenges in getting access to legal documents or renewing expired ones. In the past, police operations of massive arrests, as the aforementioned ‘Xenios Zeus’ operation, especially in the city of Athens, based on racialised characteristics ended up in detention in the PRDCs. Since most of those arrested have reportedly been found not to violate the conditions of legal stay, the spectacle of these operations that has been repeatedly circulated in public media and propagated by authorities as a means to re-establish public order have cultivated a common sense of massive irregularity. Detention has again a key role in this, since it has been used both as an excessive means for identification and as a ‘remedy’.

Official statistics reveal the key role of detention in the overall infrastructure of forced removal in Greece. According to data published by Refugee Support Aegean (RSA, 2024), 29,869 removal orders were issued by the Hellenic Police in 2023:¹³ about two out of three return orders were based on Law 3907/2011 transposing the Return Directive, and one out of three based on Law 3386/2005, in derogation from the Return Directive¹⁴. During the same year, the Hellenic Police issued more than 24,000 detention orders. Among them more than 10,000 were under Law 3907/2011 and roughly the same number were under Law 3386/2005.

¹³ In comparison with roughly 30,600 in 2022 and 21,000 in 2021.

¹⁴ Return and deportation procedures are based in two different legal acts, one transposing the return Directive (Law 3907/2011) and one earlier concerning deportation (Law 3386/2005). Their different scope is not well defined but in practice the older law is implemented in combination with a derogation from the newer one and the former leads to a much higher proportion of detention than the latter (RSA & PRO ASYL, 2022).

This means that more than 53% of return decisions according to the Return Directive and more than 96% of deportation decisions outside the scope of the Directive ended up in detention orders. Another more than 3,600 detention orders were issued for applicants of international protection, namely under the Reception Conditions Directive. At the end of the year there were 2,303 migrants in detention, 2,042 in the six PRDCs and 261 in police stations.

The detention orders are rather seldom contested. The first existing mechanism to challenge a detention order is an administrative appeal before the police, i.e. the same authority that issues detention orders in the first place, in a deadline of five days. Only 1.2% of those issued in 2023 were appealed and among these only 6% were accepted, that is merely 22 cases among almost 30,000 detention orders. According to RSA (2024), the reason behind this is the absence of any free legal assistance that persists in the country, despite the Council of the EU recommendation to Greece to revise this practice. Secondly, detainees may challenge administrative detention by lodging an objection before administrative courts. In 2023 approximately 5,000 such objections were lodged and almost half of them were granted. In various cases the ECtHR has found the objectives procedure to be ineffective, failing to examine the lawfulness of detention, including detention conditions (GCR-ECRE, 2024). The absence of free legal assistance applies here as well. Thirdly, an automatic procedure of *ex officio* review of detention orders (or of the extension of the detention period) by the administrative courts also exists. Despite that this procedure uses the same criteria and is performed by the same courts which judge objections, it turns out to no more than 0.5% of orders found unlawful (RSA, 2024).

The nationalities of detainees reveal some important patterns. In 2023 almost 4,500 detention orders concerned Pakistani citizens. They were followed by citizens of Albania, Afghanistan, Syria and Somalia, while other countries of origin of those detained include Egypt, Palestine, Eritrea, Bangladesh and Georgia. Interestingly, different countries of origin exhibit different distributions among the various pathways to detention. Thus, the population of Pakistani detainees is almost equally divided between those detained under the Return Directive and asylum seekers detained under the Reception Conditions Directive. Other third country nationals, especially the Albanians and to some extent Bangladeshis and Georgians are mainly detained under the Return Directive. Interestingly, people from countries with high percentages of recognition as beneficiaries of international protection and where return is practically impossible (Afghanistan, Somalia, Palestine, Eritrea and to some extent Syria) are mainly detained under the deportation procedure, in derogation from the Return Directive. It seems that the Hellenic Police use the derogation from the Return Directive in order to detain people who have greater possibility to be recognised as refugees and thus to irregularise them in advance.

Figure 4: Main nationalities in immigration detention: 2023

Source: RSA, 2024.

The period of detention is often prolonged. The maximum period of six plus twelve months stipulated by European law is often exhausted and sometimes violated, no matter whether a removal is practically feasible or not. Nonetheless, even after a release, one can be arrested and detained again.

As for detention conditions, they have repeatedly been found to violate basic human rights and dignity by various agents, such as the Greek Refugee Council, the Greek Ombudsman and the European Committee for the Prevention of Torture and Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (CPT). According to the last update of the AIDA country report (GCR-ECRE, 2024) several issues persisted up to 2023 in PRDCs, including ‘a carceral, prison-like design, the lack of sufficient hygiene and non-food items, including clothes and shoes, clean mattresses and clean blankets, the lack of recreational activities, and overcrowding’. The conditions for those detained in police stations are even harsher, for example with no outdoor access, lack of natural light and insufficient food¹⁵.

Medical staff shortage has also been repeatedly confirmed, but only marginal improvement occurred, if at all. For example, in 2023 there were two doctors in the PRDC of Amygdaleza (near Athens) for an official capacity of 1,000 detainees, only one doctor in the PRDC in Corinth for an official capacity of 1,344 and no doctors in the PRDCs of Paranesti and Kos.

¹⁵ See GCR-OXFAM (2021) for a collection of telling testimonies from detention centres and police stations.

7. Concluding remarks

This working paper explored how irregularisation as a process is reproduced through the legal and institutional framework of migration and asylum in the case of Greece. Irregularisation was examined and discussed as an outcome of migration and asylum policies, institutional frameworks, the political and socio-economic contexts, as well as their interplay with the formal and informal practices of various actors. The above was examined by focusing on the functioning of the European asylum system since 2015 and its particular implementation in Greece, highlighting how these reproduce aspects of irregularisation.

As noted in section 2, the irregularisation of migration is by no means a Greek phenomenon. Other member states and the EU as a whole continue to perceive migration as a major threat and in tandem with securitisation of the European borders, irregularisation has been a key priority for the European migration regime(s). However, developments in Greece may have been the model for wider policy reorientation and have offered institutional tools to implement it. For example, the events at the Greek-Turkish borders in March 2020 for which the European Commission President, Ursula von der Leyen praised Greece for being the shield of Europe, seem to have been one of the founding acts of the European discourse on 'hybrid threats' and the instrumentalisation of migration by third countries. Similarly, commenting on the whole array of regulations and procedures introduced by the 2024 Pact, Statewatch (2024) argues that 'the newly introduced screening and border procedures will lead to more people, including children and families, being held in prison-like detention facilities modelled on the Closed Controlled Access Centres already operating in Greece'.

Irregularisation in Greece, is reproduced in various ways by the migration regime and the recently transformed asylum system. The present Working Paper analysed a number of relevant procedural and institutional aspects interrelated with the three different layers of irregularisation, the spatial, the temporal, and the carceral. More particularly, the Working Paper examined how irregularisation is reproduced through the immigration system and its transformations over the last three decades including both the extremely difficult and complicated regularisation procedures and regulations on paper, and the institutional practices of the actors involved, such as the police operations that impact irregularisation processes and experiences. Increasing restrictions and legal complexity, together with supranational arrangements and geopolitical currents, have made 'regularity' more difficult to reach, as it is subject to preconditions that are often too demanding or impossible, while certain types of regular status are now for many more uncertain, precarious and fragile.

Irregularisation was also redefined after the changes in asylum laws that followed the so-called 'refugee crisis' of 2015-'16, which created a 'labyrinth' of asylum procedures that were difficult to navigate. In this labyrinth, spatialities and temporalities of irregularisation may vary, as procedures are usually characterised by temporal discontinuity and are differentiated according to distinct geographies. As also noted in the Working Paper, law implementation is much more complex than procedures on paper, while an inverse trajectory is observed, one in which the intention to remove migrants is the starting point and illegality is the outcome. In this regard, detention is also a determinant of this labyrinth. Detention is a common practice during the asylum application and registration process both in the border islands (at the RICs or the CCACs), and in the mainland (through the process of the online platform and the appointment in a camp). It may also concern people who have already applied for international protection and are detained even after their application. Even though border controls had been gradually tightening, applying for asylum, even if knowing that this had limited possibilities for a successful outcome and being aware that it could involve detention in case of arrest, had been a main pathway to some kind of regularity.

The asylum procedure involves different and extremely complex types of procedures, which are spatially different (between the borders and the Greek mainland), and which are not only defined in regulations on paper but also evolve over the years in an ad hoc manner, in cases that are contrary to the rule of law. Moreover, aspects of irregularisation refer to a range of ‘irregular’ practices that people with ‘regular’ status, such as asylum seekers, may use to navigate the restrictive asylum and reception system. These may include practices of mobility and settlement that are not permitted by the system –or are even criminalised by it– as asylum seekers who engage in them may lose certain asylum and reception provisions. This fact illustrates how irregularisation may be reproduced even during the examination of an asylum claim, i.e. while people are entitled to asylum provisions.

Irregularisation in the case of Greece also emerges due to the process of safe third-country inadmissibility and its particular implementation in the country, combined with the fact that readmissions to Turkey have been suspended since March 2020. A wide ‘grey zone’ has been created and thousands of applicants for international protection were exposed to legal limbo, the risk of detention, and exclusion from protection and reception conditions. Furthermore, irregularisation emerges during the processes of asylum decision notification which may expire without the applicant being informed about asylum rejections; the same concerns processes of appeals and judicial reviews since in particular cases, they do not have an automatic suspensive effect of the return decision they incorporate. As regards the return framework this is characterised by ambiguity, by reproducing aspects of irregularisation due to the co-existence of different Laws. This fact permits the maintenance of the police practice of issuing expulsion decisions against TCNs irregularly entering Greece at the borders even if they subsequently apply for international protection and obtain a permit to stay in the country. Also, self-irregularisation emerges during the AVRR program. This is because enrolment in the program and its provisions presupposes that the migrants should abandon or withdraw their asylum applications or any rights deriving from a regular status and remain in an irregular status for a short (but indeterminate) period before their return.

The Working Paper also attempted a conceptual and theoretical contribution concerning the notion: irregularisation is not perceived as a stable or static characteristic of an individual or a group of people, or as a fixed category of legal status that some migrants do not possess while others do. Rather, irregularisation emerges as a process in which many people (also of ‘regular’ status) may be involved, in sequences of (ir)regular statuses, a process unfolding at the intersections of the spatial, the temporal, and the carceral layer, as an inherently spatio-temporal process.

Spatiality and temporality in the process of irregularisation is constitutive even before border-crossing, but also during the diverse routes along which legislation and institutional practices categorise people, places, and periods of time. The spatialities of irregularisation are interconnected with the spatiality of borders, not merely the lines that separate states, but those multiplied and transferred beyond border zones, both externally and internally within the nation-state. At the same time, irregularisation is not only reproduced at the borders, but through procedures and institutional frameworks that create borders, categories, restrictions, carceralities. Indicatively, as argued in the paper, spaces of irregularisation are defined through the asylum system itself, during the entire process of applying for asylum, including different facilities that range from those of detention to those of refugee identification, reception and accommodation. The boundaries of spaces of (il)legal, (ir)regular, registered, detained, to-be-returned, deportee, asylum-seeker are blurred, as are the experiences, statuses, and spectrums of irregularisation of those emplaced in these spaces. Time is also essential. The migration and asylum system is characterised by different stages and sequences,

diverging paces and tempos, timeframes and deadlines, durations and temporalities. These are not given or stable but rather fluid as they may change over time along shifts and changes in laws and policies, and reflect variably on migrants' subjective experiences, coping practices and adapting trajectories in periods of waiting or acceleration, in moments 'before', 'during' and 'after', in forward moves but also reversals or even loops. In its temporal dimension, irregularisation begins at the borders, sometimes before their crossings, and accompany migrants' trajectories throughout the migration and asylum system, the asylum procedure, the spaces of waiting for –or acceleration of– the procedures.

Space and time, inherently interconnected in the constitution of irregularisation as a process define migrants' experiences. Irregularisation involves multiple categories and conditions of irregularity, characterised as fluid and not clear-cut, not only at the edges of the legal and illegal but also at the whole spectrum in between. Moreover, irregularisation as a process is broader than the sequences and the interplay of the multiple and different (ir)regular statuses as it may also include a number of informal or irregular practices that 'regular' people develop in order to navigate in the otherwise hostile migration and asylum system. The interrelations of irregularisation to the changing political conjunctures, the socioeconomic contexts, and the employment/labour needs that deem a migrant as 'deserving' protection, asylum, regularisation, etc. may thus reveal how irregularisation is not only produced by laws and their implementation but is productive in itself.

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